

INTERFACIAL INVESTIGATIONS AND MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF CARBON NANOTUBE REINFORCING Al_2O_3 NANOCOMPOSITES

I. Ahmad*, M. Fay⁺, A. Kennedy*, Y. Q. Zhu^{**}

*Division of Materials, Mechanics & Structures, Faculty of Engineering,
The University of Nottingham, University Park, NG7 2RD, UK.
Email: Yanqiu.zhu@nottingham.ac.uk

⁺Nottingham NanoScience and NanoTechnology Centre (NNNC),
The University of Nottingham, University Park, Nottingham,
NG7 2RD, UK.

SUMMARY

Carbon nanotubes (CNTs) reinforced Al_2O_3 nanocomposites have been fabricated by hot-pressing. 32% and 35% improvement in fracture toughness was observed at 2 wt % and 5 wt % CNTs reinforcement, respectively, according to ISB techniques. Well-dispersed CNTs within the Al_2O_3 matrix, crack-bridging phenomenon by CNTs, CNTs elastic characteristics and strong interfacial connection between CNTs- Al_2O_3 lead to nanocomposites with superior mechanical properties.

Keywords: Carbon Nanotubes, Nanocomposite, Fracture toughness, Interface

INTRODUCTION

Recent advances in nanotechnology have opened new ways to tailor the materials at the nanoscale, in order to improve various properties. Among other nanomaterials carbon nanotubes (CNTs) show highly attractive mechanical, electrical and thermal properties, and are thus of great interest in materials research for the development of multi-functional materials to meet the requirements of advanced engineering applications [1, 2]. With a tubular structure, CNTs are considered the strongest material ever known, with high tensile strength (~30-60 GPa) and elastic modulus ~ 1 TPa [2]. These excellent properties of CNTs can be exploited by employing them as reinforcement in various organic and inorganic matrices and this appears to be one of the hottest topics in current research activities relating to advanced materials. Significant improvement in the mechanical properties has been reported by incorporating CNTs into a polymer matrix [3]. In contrast to polymer matrices, far less attention has been given to develop CNTs-ceramics nanocomposites. In a few such efforts, the CNTs were used to reinforce various ceramics matrices, such as Al_2O_3 , SiC and Si_3N_4 and significant improvement in the fracture toughness and other mechanical properties have been reported with low additions of CNTs (< 2 wt %) however, unsatisfactory results were reported with higher CNTs additions [4-6].

Al_2O_3 or alumina has a wide range of applications such as in high speed cutting tools, dental implants, chemical and electrical insulators, wear resistance parts and various coatings due to its high hardness, chemical inertness, high electrical and thermal

insulation properties. However, it is not considered as a good candidate for advanced structural and aerospace applications including aircraft engine parts, rocket materials surviving in extreme environments and numerous other space engineering applications due to its inferior fracture toughness. Various materials such as metals (Fe, Co, Ni), ceramics (SiC, MgO, ZrO) and carbon fibers have been reinforced to improve the fracture toughness of monolithic Al₂O₃ and notable improvement was reported [7]. It is believed that CNTs can upgrade Al₂O₃ and make it suitable for numerous advanced applications. Recently Al₂O₃ was reinforced with various amounts of CNTs and consolidated by using different sintering processes however, wide differences in the mechanical and physical properties were found [8-12]. The main problems associated with the CNTs-ceramics nanocomposites are agglomeration of CNTs, inadequate densification and weak CNTs-ceramic interfacial connections [13].

In this paper, the effects of various amounts of CNTs (2 and 5 wt %) on the mechanical properties of Al₂O₃-CNTs nanocomposites, in particular the fracture toughness are presented. In particular, structural features of nanocomposites and interfacial connections developed during the hot pressing at high temperatures and high pressures condition will be discussed.

EXPERIMENTAL TECHNIQUES

Fabrication of Nanocomposites

CNTs having diameters ~ 40 nm (Tsinghua University, Beijing, China) were well-dispersed within Al₂O₃ nanopowder ($\Phi < 40$ nm, obtained from Sigma Aldrich, UK). Dried Al₂O₃/CNTs mixtures were then consolidated by hot-pressing in a graphite die under a pressure of 40 MPa at 1600°C for 60 min, at heating rate of 10 °C/min, under vacuum (6.2×10^{-2} Pa) at University of Mining and Technology, Beijing, China and discs of the nanocomposites ($\Phi 32 \times 3$ mm) were finally obtained. Monolithic Al₂O₃ was also hot-pressed under identical experimental conditions for comparison.

Structural Characterisation

Structural features of the fractured samples were assessed by scanning electron microscopy (SEM), and images were acquired using secondary electron (SE) signals. Prior to SEM observation, the samples were gold coated for 1 min. X-ray diffraction (XRD, Siemens D500 and Bruker D8 Advanced X-ray Diffractometer, using Cu k_{α} radiation) was employed to identify the crystalline phase features of the nanocomposites, with the assistance of computer software (DIFFRAC^{plus} and by Bruker Advanced X-ray Solutions). SEM and XRD techniques were also employed to determine the sample grain sizes. Transmission electron microscopy (TEM, JEOL 2000 FX and 2100 F) were used to characterise the interface structures of the nanocomposites. TEM samples were prepared by deep etching using NaOH for two weeks followed by a thorough rinsing with distilled water in order to remove traces of NaOH. The clean samples were dispersed in acetone and then transferred onto a holey carbon film, supported on a copper grid, for observation.

Density Measurement

Archimedes method was employed to measure the densities of the samples (using distilled water), and the relative densities were calculated by dividing the apparent density by the theoretical density. In this study, 3.9 g/cm^3 and 1.85 g/cm^3 were assumed for the theoretical densities for Al_2O_3 and CNTs, respectively.

Mechanical Properties Evaluation

A standard ultrasonic pulse-echo method was adopted to estimate the elastic modulus of the monolithic Al_2O_3 and the CNTs reinforced nanocomposites. In this technique, the time-of-flight velocities for both compression and shear wave propagating through the samples were recorded. Compression measurements were made using 20 MHz centre frequency, Φ 6 mm, contact transducers (TMP-3, Sonatest, UK). The equivalent shear measurements were performed with a 10 MHz centre frequency, Φ 10 mm, contact transducer (V221-BA, Panametrics, USA). Suitable couplant materials were used in each case to ensure optimum contact between the samples and transducer. From the velocity measurements elastic modulus of samples were calculated by employing following equation [14]:

$$E = \frac{V_s^2 \rho (3V_c^2 - 4V_s^2)}{V_c^2 - V_s^2}$$

where E is the Young's modulus, ρ is the bulk density of the samples, V_c is the compression velocity and V_s the shear velocity.

For hardness evaluation, the sintered nanocomposite samples were sliced using a resin-bonded diamond disc cutter and cold mounted. During cold mounting, the samples were vacuum infiltrated using epoxy resin. After mounting, the samples were first ground on diamond pads of 120 and 220 grit and then polished to 6 micron and 1 micron by using DP-Suspension on polishing cloths. Microhardness testing was carried out at 9.8 N loads for 15 sec (M-400 hardness tester, LECO, Japan). The diagonal lengths of the indent were measured using the attached microscope, converted to Vickers hardness number (HV) and further converted to GPa [15].

The indentation strength in bending (ISB) method was adopted to evaluate the fracture toughness. In the ISB method, three samples ($25 \pm 1.5 \text{ mm}$ (length) \times $2 \pm 0.15 \text{ mm}$ (breadth) \times $2.5 \pm 0.20 \text{ mm}$ (height)) were sliced from nanocomposite disc using a resin impregnated diamond cutter and polished down to 1 micron with diamond paste, to eliminate surface defects caused by the cutting process. An indent was made at the middle of each sample employing a hardness tester with a diamond Vickers indenter using a load of 10 kg (98.066 N). This load was carefully selected to ensure that the crack size was above the critical size, in order to obtain meaningful results. Three point bending test was carried out with the bending span of 20 mm at a testing speed of 0.50 mm/min. All the samples broke exactly where the indent was made. The fracture toughness was then calculated using following equation [16]:

$$K_{IC} = 0.59 \left(\frac{E}{H} \right)^{1/8} (\sigma P^{1/3})^{3/4}$$

where E is the Young's modulus, H is the hardness, σ the flexural strength in the presence of the Vickers indent and P the load at failure.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Dispersion of CNTs and Structural Features

Dispersion of CNTs within the Al_2O_3 matrix is extremely important for a high quality nanocomposite. Well-dispersed CNTs lead nanocomposites to higher density and good mechanical properties, while in other case when CNTs are present in the form of agglomerates or lumps, due to Van der Waal interaction and high aspect ratio, they acted as impurities thus showing no reinforcement effects [17]. Figure 1 displays a SEM image of fractured surface of the nanocomposite, exhibiting well-dispersed CNTs within the matrix. The dispersion of CNTs was achieved by combined action of surfactant, SDS (sodium dodecyl sulphate), ultrasonic stirring and sufficient incubation for thorough adsorption of SDS on CNTs surface, which counteract the Van der Waal interactions [17].

Figure 1: Well-dispersed CNTs within Al_2O_3 matrix.

XRD patterns of the sintered monolithic Al_2O_3 (JCPDS No. 01-078-2426) and graphite (JCPD No. 01-075-1621) for the pristine CNTs are displayed in Figures 2a and 2b. The patterns of sintered Al_2O_3 -CNTs nanocomposites, Figures 2c and 2d, revealed only the typical crystalline peaks from α - Al_2O_3 and no peaks from CNTs were observed. The diminishing of CNTs peaks are possibly due to high crystallinity of Al_2O_3 phase and low contents of CNTs in the nanocomposites.

Figure 2: XRD patterns of (a) pristine CNTs, (b) α - Al_2O_3 , (c) Al_2O_3 -2 wt % CNTs nanocomposite and (d) Al_2O_3 -5 wt % CNTs nanocomposite.

Densification and Grain Size

Effects of various CNTs contents on the density of Al_2O_3 can be observed in Figure 3. A relative density of 99.67% was achieved for monolithic Al_2O_3 . The nanocomposites with 2 wt % CNTs showed negligible difference (0.5%) in relative density however, a significant drop (3 %) in relative density was observed with 5 wt % additions, as shown in Figure 3. Elimination of pores and mass transportation through bulk diffusion are two important factors that determine the final density during the consolidation of Al_2O_3 [18]. It is believed that the introduction of CNTs into the Al_2O_3 matrix adversely affected these two important sintering parameters and consequently resulted in nanocomposites with lower densities [18].

Figure 3: Relative density and grain size of Al_2O_3 as a function of CNTs additions.

Figure 4: Fractured surface SEM image of, (a) monolithic Al_2O_3 , (b) Al_2O_3 -2 wt % CNTs nanocomposite and (c) Al_2O_3 -5 wt % CNTs nanocomposite.

Grain boundaries are favourable location for CNTs in the nanocomposites therefore, inhabitation of grain growth occurred during the consolidation process, resulting in nanocomposites with a submicron grain size, Figure 3. A sharp decrease (96%) in grain size can be observed with 2 wt % CNTs addition when compared with monolithic Al_2O_3 . Further addition of CNTs up to 5 wt % did not show any significant difference in grain size. Therefore, it can be assumed that addition of more CNTs raises the CNTs population at grain boundaries instead of pinning more grains.

Fractured surface investigation further confirmed the reduction of grain size with increasing CNT content (Figures 4a and 4c). Moreover, CNTs changed the mode of fracture from inter-granular fracture in monolithic Al_2O_3 , Figure 4a, to trans-granular fracture in nanocomposites (Figures 4b and 4c). This phenomenal change of fracture mode can be attributed to the strengthening of grain boundary by CNTs. Fracture mechanics studies of ceramics-based composites indicated that the strengthening effects of inter-granular residual stress on grain boundaries increased with the second phase addition. When the strength of grain boundary reached to that of matrix grain, trans-granular fracture occurred [19]. Change of fracture mode also can be indicative of higher mechanical properties of the nanocomposites

Fracture Toughness and other Mechanical Properties

12% increase in hardness and 32% increase in fracture toughness were observed with 2 wt % CNTs addition, however further addition of CNTs, up to 5 wt %, slightly suppressed the hardness (7%), but increased the fracture toughness (35%), compared with those of monolithic Al_2O_3 , Figure 5. The increase in mechanical properties at low CNTs additions (2 wt %) can be associated with the well-dispersed CNTs within the matrix, load sharing between the matrix and CNTs, by bridge cracking phenomenon and strong interfacial connection between CNTs and matrix. The decrease in hardness at higher CNTs addition (5 wt %) may be due to the densification difficulties arising with higher concentrations of CNTs in the nanocomposites.

Figure 5: Effects of CNTs addition on the fracture toughness and hardness of nanocomposites.

The promising increase in fracture toughness can be associated with the contribution of CNT's mechanical properties during nanocomposite deformation by a crack bridging mechanism. CNTs have a high elasticity ~ 1 TPa, which has been predicted by various theoretical models and experimental techniques [21]. It is believed that the energy dissipation mechanism operative during nanocomposite fracture can be attributed to the

work done by the extension of the CNTs over a distance at the ends of fractured surfaces. Furthermore, this phenomenon is not of primary concern in conventional fibre-reinforced composites but is of significance for nanocomposites, due to their excellent elastic properties and dimensional effect [20].

Interfacial Investigations

To exploit the elastic properties of CNTs in nanocomposites, a strong interfacial connection between matrix and CNTs is essential. TEM and high-resolution TEM images, Figures 6a and 6b, clearly demonstrate the firm attachments of CNT with the Al_2O_3 matrix. Our recent investigations concerned with the interfacial connection between CNTs and Al_2O_3 indicated that Al_2O_3 underwent carbo-thermal reduction in the presence of reducing atmosphere (being CNTs in this case), and formed interfacial aluminium-oxy-carbide (Al_2OC) layer at Al_2O_3 /CNT interfaces. Presumably this phase has good compatibility with both the matrix and the CNTs, and is thus capable of transferring load from the matrix to CNTs and vice versa [21]. In addition, a thin layer of Al_2OC sheathed the CNTs and restricted them from further reaction with the matrix. Our study has showed the existence of CNT in its original morphology and structure, even after processing, as demonstrated in Figure 1 and Figure 6 where the curved morphology of CNT is visible with fringe separation of 0.34 nm corresponding to the (002) planes. Therefore, in the presence of such strong interfaces, the matrix firmly holds the strong CNTs in their original morphology and structure, leading to enhanced mechanical properties, particularly fracture toughness.

Figure 6: (a) TEM image showing interface in Al_2O_3 -CNTs nanocomposite, (b) High resolution-TEM lattice resolved image of Al_2O_3 -CNTs nanocomposite interface.

CONCLUSIONS

Well-dispersed CNTs within the Al_2O_3 matrix have been successfully obtained by the combination of surfactant (SDS) addition, ultrasonic stirring and adequate incubation time (2 weeks). The resulting nanocomposites exhibited near theoretical density (99.29%) for 2 wt % CNTs additions, however further addition up to 5 wt % led to slightly suppressed (96.29%) density. A 12% increase in hardness and 32% increase in

fracture toughness were observed with 2 wt % CNT addition, when compared with monolithic Al₂O₃. The presence of CNTs in an Al₂O₃ matrix possibility exhibited two major functions, (a) decreased the sintered density of nanocomposite due to their existence at grain boundary, which hindered achieving full density of the nanocomposite and (b) sharply reduced the grain size by restricting grain growth. Mechanically, the improvement in properties is due to a load sharing phenomenon, which was carried out by bridging the crack surfaces by CNTs during crack propagation under applied load and a strong interface between CNTs and Al₂O₃ matrix. Furthermore, the extraordinary elastic characteristics of CNTs also contributed to the improvement of fracture toughness.

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